

ESN with delayed inputs to model industrial processes

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Abstract. Modeling industrial processes is essential for optimizing performance and detecting anomalies, particularly in complex systems with delayed responses. Echo State Networks (ESNs) have demonstrated efficiency in modeling dynamic systems due to their simple and fast training process. However, standard ESNs do not account for the delayed effects of input variables, which are common in industrial environments. This work introduces a Delayed Input Echo State Network to better capture the time-dependent relationships in process modeling.

The proposed method is applied to real data from the AQUASOL-II solar plant at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), focusing on modeling output temperatures in solar collector loops. Three architectures are compared: a standard ESN, an ESN with a uniform input delay, and an ESN with independent delays for each variable. Results show that this delayed approach can improve the accuracy of the models compared to both traditional ESNs and physics-based models. These findings highlight the potential of an ESN with delayed inputs for real-time industrial applications, offering a balance between computational efficiency and performance.

Keywords: Data Mining · Echo State Networks · Industrial Process Modeling · Real Data

1 Introduction

Industrial processes are becoming increasingly complex, making their management and monitoring more challenging. Modeling these systems is crucial for understanding their behavior, detecting anomalies, and optimizing performance, leading to greater efficiency and reduced energy consumption [16]. However, industrial environments generate vast amounts of fast-changing data, making it

difficult to extract meaningful insights [15]. A model that closely represents the real system is essential for accurate analysis.

Machine learning, particularly *Recurrent Neural Networks* (RNNs), have proven to be effective in modeling dynamic systems, especially time-series data [10]. RNNs capture temporal dependencies using recurrent connections, enabling them to represent complex, nonlinear behaviors [17]. Deep learning further enhances modeling capabilities by identifying even more complex patterns in data, but its high computational demands can make it infeasible for industrial applications [11]. Advances in workload distribution and GPUs have addressed some of these challenges, making deep learning more accessible [14].

Despite these improvements, real-time industrial applications require fast, lightweight and efficient models. *Long Short-Term Memory* (LSTM) networks, a type of RNN, are effective for time-series forecasting but can suffer from slow convergence and stability issues [18]. *Reservoir Computing* (RC) offers an alternative with faster training and lower hardware demands by generating a fixed, randomly initialized recurrent layer (the reservoir) and training only the output layer [20].

Echo State Networks (ESNs), an implementation of Reservoir Computing, are valued for their simplicity, efficiency, and adaptability. They can adapt to system changes by updating only the output weights, avoiding the need to retrain the entire model [13]. Due to their efficiency and adaptability, ESNs are promising for industrial modeling, yet most studies focus on simulations rather than real-world applications [19]. In this work, ESNs are applied to a real industrial system of a solar plant sited in Almería to model the output temperature of the solar panels. A ESN model with delayed input is implemented to consider the delay introduced by the heating process in the real system [2].

This work is structured as follows: section 2 describes the architecture of a Echo State Network with delayed inputs. Section 3 explains the structure of the industrial process analyzed (AQUASOL-II pilot plant). In section 4 the results obtained with the proposed model are presented. Finally, Section 5 draws conclusions and discusses future work.

2 Echo State Networks

Echo State Networks (ESN) [7] are based on the concept of a *reservoir*, a high-dimensional hidden layer that processes input signals and generates a rich representation of the input data. The reservoir is a randomly generated network of interconnected recurrent nodes that are typically sparsely connected and have fixed weights. The output is generated by a linear readout layer that maps the reservoir’s high-dimensional representation to the desired output. For this reason, ESNs offer an efficient and effective alternative to traditional RNNs [5], as they are easier to train and require fewer parameters. The reservoir acts as a non-linear, high-dimensional dynamical system, which maps an input vector $\mathbf{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_U}$ of dimension N_U into a state vector $\mathbf{x}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ with N_R reservoir states.

The most common variation of this architecture incorporates a leaky integrator mechanism to modulate the recall of previous states [8]. This variant, known as Leaky Integrator ESN (LI-ESN), is the one used in this work and it responds to the following state equation:

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{x}(k - 1) + \alpha \phi(\mathbf{W}_{\text{res}} \mathbf{x}(k - 1) + \mathbf{W}_{\text{in}} \mathbf{u}(k) + \theta). \quad (1)$$

In this equation, $\mathbf{x}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ represents the reservoir state at time k , while $\mathbf{u}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_U}$ denotes the input vector. The weights of the reservoir connections are defined by $\mathbf{W}_{\text{res}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_R}$, and the input-to-reservoir weights are given by $\mathbf{W}_{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_U}$. The vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ introduces a bias to the input. The leak rate $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the influence of previous states on the current reservoir state, while ϕ represents the activation function applied element-wise, typically a hyperbolic tangent or sigmoid function.

The readout mechanism translates the reservoir states into an N_Y -dimensional output vector $\mathbf{y}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y}$ using a linear transformation. The weights of this transformation are the only parameters trained in the ESN, typically optimized via standard least-squares regression. The output equation is given by:

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \mathbf{W}_{\text{out}} \mathbf{x}(k) + \theta_{\text{out}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y}$ represents the output vector at time k , $\mathbf{W}_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y \times N_R}$ denotes the reservoir-to-readout weight matrix, and $\theta_{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Y}$ is the bias vector applied to the output.

The weight matrices \mathbf{W}_{res} and \mathbf{W}_{in} are initialized with random values and specific adjustments are made to promote the desired dynamic behavior in the reservoir. To achieve sparsity, most elements in these matrices are set to zero, leaving only a small fraction of non-zero weights distributed randomly. In addition, the reservoir weight matrix \mathbf{W}_{res} is scaled to ensure that the reservoir satisfy the so-called Echo State Property (ESP) [4], maintaining its dynamics on the edge of stability.

When the reservoir processes an input sequence $\{\mathbf{u}(k)\}_{k=1}^{N_k}$ iteratively, it generates a sequence of high-dimensional reservoir state vectors $\{\mathbf{x}(k)\}_{k=1}^{N_k}$. These state vectors are then combined linearly in the readout layer using trainable weights to produce the output sequence $\{\mathbf{y}(k)\}_{k=1}^{N_k}$. This readout weight matrix \mathbf{W}_{out} is usually computed using the *ridge regression* method [12].

2.1 Echo State Network with Delayed Input

In some scenarios, especially when dealing with real systems, the action of the input has a delayed effect on the action of the system and the accuracy of the model can be improved by taking these delays into account.

The idea of creating a system in which the inputs are delayed is presented in [9]. In this work, it is simply proposed to insert a delay layer between the input and the reservoir, in which the delay that this control action has on the system is introduced as an additional hyperparameter. Thus, the state equation of the ESN is as follows:

Fig. 1. Structure of an ESN with a delay layer.

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{x}(k - 1) + \alpha \phi(\mathbf{W}_{\text{res}} \mathbf{x}(k - 1) + \mathbf{W}_{\text{in}} \mathbf{u}(k - t) + \theta) \quad (3)$$

In this equation, the vector $\mathbf{u}(k-t)$ is $[u_1(k-t_1), u_2(k-t_2), \dots, u_{N_U}(k-t_{N_U})]$, composed of the N_U inputs of the system u_i , each one with a t_i delay time. These delay times t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{N_U} can be the same or different for each input variable. This delay can vary depending on the type of physical variable, and in this case the number of hyperparameters of the ESN model may be quite large. However, the short training time of the network allows to test a large number of different trials in a short time.

The architecture of an ESN with a delayed input is depicted in Figure 1, where bias terms have been omitted for clarity. This structure is similar to the structure of a standard ESN, which has the following layers: the *input* layer, the *reservoir* layer, and the *readout* or *output* layer. In this work, an additional fourth layer is added between the input and the reservoir, the *delay* layer, which takes as parameters the number of samples that each input is delayed with respect to the current samples. If the delayed input variable has no previous values (i.e. at the beginning of the input sequence), that variable is considered to have a value of zero.

3 Physical System and Dataset

The proposed ESN models are tested in The AQUASOL-II solar field, located at the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA) in Spain (Fig. 2). This facility provides thermal energy for a variety of thermal desalination technologies as well as for an innovative cooling pilot plant.

The solar field consists of 60 stationary flat-plate solar collectors (Wagner LBM 10HTF) connected to a thermal storage system through a heat exchanger.

Fig. 2. AQUASOL-II solar field facility at PSA (Spain).

Table 1. System variables

Variable Type	Variable Name	Unit
Ambient Variables	Ambient Temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
	Global solar irradiance (35°)	W/m^2
Process Variables	Loop 2 Row1 Tracker	Degrees
	Loop 2 Row2 Tracker	Degrees
	Loop 2 Flow rate	m^3/s
	Loop 2 Temp In	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
	Loop 2 Temp Out	$^{\circ}\text{C}$

These collectors are arranged in parallel loops, as shown in Figure 3: 4 of the loops contain 14 collectors distributed in two rows and connected in series, while another smaller loop consists of 4 collectors in one row.

All the loops of the solar field are then connected to a common manifold which delivers energy to the heat exchanger and, in turn, to a water storage system (acting as a heat buffer). The stored hot water can be used to operate other facilities, such as a multi-effect thermal desalination plant or a steam generator of a cooling pilot plant. Each loop is equipped with a pumping system to control the water flow rate. The position of the solar collectors is fixed, but they have an adjustable solar tracker with a mirror, whose angle can be modified to maximize the solar radiation that reaches these collectors.

The normal operating cycle of the solar field is to start the system in the early morning to provide heat to the storage system. The operating setpoint is maintained throughout the day, and the system is shut down in the late afternoon, releasing the residual heat from the system. In normal operation, all the loops operate identically since the flow pump setpoint is the same, so the flow rate through each loop is expected to be the same, and as the panels are identical, the heat supplied to the fluid will be also the same.

Fig. 3. Diagram of the Solar Field.

In this paper, only the Loop 2 is modeled, using the variables listed in the table 1. The output variable of the model is the output temperature of the loop and the input variables are the input temperature, the flow rate, the position of the solar trackers and the ambient variables.

The experiments performed use data from operation cycles conducted in November, December, and January. A total of 42 operation cycles were recorded, with data sampled every 1 minute, resulting in 19,145 samples. The data is pre-processed to remove periods when the system was inactive, as the focus is solely on analyzing the operation of the system. In addition, the data is normalized to maintain a consistent scale and minimize the impact of potential outliers.

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithms, the results are compared with the temperature estimated by means of a model obtained from the physical equations of the system. This model, presented in [2], obtains good results when the delays of the variables involved in the process are considered as parameters.

4 Results

In this work, three different ESN architectures are proposed to analyze how the delays in the input variables affect the output of the models. First, we propose a standard ESN in which the inputs have no delay, second, we consider an ESN

Fig. 4. Importance of each hyperparameter with no delay.

with the same delay for all the variables, and finally, we also consider an ESN with an independent delay for each variable. As the solar plant is started in the morning and stopped in the afternoon, and it is not necessarily started on consecutive days, the available data has gaps between each of the days recorded. This means that, when the ESN is run on data from a different day, the previous reservoir states must be reset so that the past data does not influence the modeling process.

For the experiments, since the data are available for several days and each day represents a complete cycle of operation of the solar plant, the data have been divided into batches of days, separating approximately 60% for training, 20% for validation and 20% for testing.

The *ReservoirPy* Python library [21] is used to generate and train the models, and the *Optuna* Python library [1] is chosen to find the best combinations of hyperparameters. A global search of the hyperparameters is performed for all the trained models, since training ESNs is not very time consuming. To find the best ones, 500 trials has been performed using the *Tree-structured Parzen Estimator* (TPE) searching algorithm [3]. The loss of the different models is computed using *Root Mean Squared Error* (RMSE) on the normalized data.

With the first model, a standard ESN without delayed inputs, a search for the best hyperparameters is performed to check which parameters have more influence in this scenario. The influence of the different hyperparameters is also computed with the *Optuna* library, which uses fANOVA evaluation algorithm [6]. Figure 4 shows that the parameter with the greatest influence in the performance of the model is the leaking rate, which controls the recall of previous states of the reservoir on the dynamics of the model: the smaller this parameter is, the

Fig. 5. Importance of each hyperparameter with same delay for all the input variables.

Fig. 6. Best value for the delay (samples) hyperparameter.

more static the model is and therefore the slower the changes in the model will be.

For the second model, the delay factor of the inputs is added as a hyperparameter with the same value for all variables. As the ESN has a high training speed, all hyperparameters are searched again to check the differences in the importance of the hyperparameters between this model and the one without delay. The figure 5 shows the influence of the parameters on the model performance with the same input delay for all variables. It can be seen that the most important factor is still the leaking rate, but for this model the second factor is the

Fig. 7. Importance of each hyperparameter with different delay for each input variables.

Fig. 8. Best value for delay (samples) of each input variable.

delay. This fact shows that the delay has a high influence on the performance of the model.

Table 2. Best input delay for each variable.

	Variable	Samples
ESN different delays	Track 1 Delay	8
	Track 2 Delay	8
	Temp. In Delay	0
	Flow Delay	7
	Amb. Temp. Delay	1
	Solar irradiance Delay	0

Table 3. Best validation RMSE error and selected hyperparameters.

	ESN no delay	ESN same delay	ESN different delays
RMSE	0.0177	0.0164	0.0144
Leak Rate	0.5816	0.4110	0.5605
Spectral Radius	1.1237	0.8385	0.8236
Input Connectivity	0.2422	0.1472	0.1001
RC Connectivity	0.1504	0.1237	0.1538
Bias	1.0	1.0	1.0
Ridge	0.0652	0.0884	0.0987
Reservoir Size	250	250	250

Figure 6 shows how the model error varies as a function of the delay value for the best 50 trials. In this case, it can be seen that the best delay for the model is 1 sample, which corresponds to a delay of one minute according to the sampling rate. It can also be seen that the performance of the model is worse when the delay is high.

The third tested model is the one that has an independent delay for each input variable. Figure 7 shows how the delay of each variable has a different influence on the the model. In addition, Figure 8 shows how the error of the models varies as a function of the different input delays. In this figure, it can be seen that the variables with the highest delay are the tracker and the flow. In order to make the figure clearer, only the best 100 training runs are shown. Table 2 lists the best time delay for each of the input variables.

Table 3 sums up the results of the trained models with the validation error and the best hyperparameters of each one. It can be seen that, as the delay increases, the connectivity of the input matrix is reduced, implying less complex dependencies between inputs and states, while the rest of the parameters are not very different. With regard to the output error, the ESN with different delays is the one that produces the lowest RMSE.

Finally, Table 4 and Figure 9 show the results of applying the best models obtained to the test data, including the simulation based on physical equations of the plant. It can be seen that test results are similar to the previously obtained validation errors, also having a better performance when running an ESN with different delays. The error results of the ESN models are shown as both the mean and standard deviation of several runs to prove that the model improvement is

Fig. 9. Model results for three days of the test dataset.

Table 4. Test data results

Model	RMSE
Simulation	0.04278
ESN no delay	0.01611 ± 0.0017
ESN same delay	0.01491 ± 0.0012
ESN different delays	0.01385 ± 0.0013

not dependent on the weight initialization. The output of the physical model when using the test data is also shown in the figure to demonstrate how ESNs can produce accurate models of the industrial system. In this case, the physical model does not take into account the effect of the trackers, so the error is higher.

5 Conclusions

This paper presents an application of modified *Echo State Networks* modeling real process data. In this approach, an additional layer is inserted between the input and the reservoir to introduce delays in the input signals. The main purpose is to demonstrate how this modification improves the results of ESN-based models. This is particularly useful for real physical systems where control variables influence the system with a delay. Additionally, the modified model retains the fast training capability of *Echo State Networks*.

The models were trained using real process data from the Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), a solar collector system. In this system, the output temperature can experience significant delays due to the high inertia of temperature variables. Three types of models have been trained and compared, one without input delay, another with the same delay for all the input variables and a third with a different delay for each variable.

The training process has been thoroughly tested with a wide range of parameters, taking advantage of the ease of training that ESNs provide. The results confirm that the model with a different delay for each input performs better, and that each input variable affects the process with a different delay. Additionally, the analysis shows how the performance of the models varies depending on the delay considered in each of the inputs.

The article shows how it is possible to use ESN-based models to determine the behavior of real industrial systems and how these models improve the results compared to the use of classical models based on physical equations of the process.

Future work will focus on developing more accurate system models using more complex and advanced ESN-based architectures that better capture the real structure of the process. In this regard, one possible approach is to use *Deep Echo State Networks* to represent the double-loop structure of the system. In addition, further tests will be conducted to better understand the influence of hyperparameters, allowing for a more efficient search by focusing on only the variables with a greater influence.

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